

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RELIABILITY DETERMINATION IN THE DESIGN OF NATURAL GAS PRESSURE REGULATING INSTALLATIONS

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Abstract

The publication describes the possible influences of various criteria and parameters at the design stage on the reliability and safety of gas regulating installations for natural gas during their subsequent installation and operation. The determination of structural and constructive schemes of the installation for regulating the pressure of natural gas and the ways of determining the complex reliability of the installation, as an independent system, are considered.

Keywords: Gas regulating installations; reliability of gas regulating installations; risk assessment of gas regulation installations; natural gas pressure regulation installations; gas regulating boards

1. Introduction

The design of an installation for regulating the pressure of natural gas is usually carried out by one or several teams. This depends on the size and complexity of the installation itself. Since this type of installation contains parts that require different design competencies, most often the design is carried out by several individuals or teams. Under this condition, as well as in accordance with the responsibility that the designer bears to ensure the safety and reliability of the installation designed by him, it can be expected that the project will be carried out in the best way. Very often the designer has to make compromise decisions in order to achieve the goals set before him. This is part of the process of designing this type of installations, and at the same time, the designer who made the compromise decision must inform the person who assigned him the design of the gas regulation installation about his decision and prove that it will not affect negatively on the reliability and safety of the designed facility. One of the most important compromises that can arise before the designer is the expediency of the adopted technical solution. Very often, designers are faced with the dilemma of which material to prefer, is it possible to choose some basic elements, units and aggregates with lower prices at the expense of losing some of their functional characteristics or capabilities, etc. The special thing about the design of such gas regulation installations is that in most cases they are different from each other, such as the technical solution, arrangement of the elements, diameters of the pipe lines and the corresponding fittings, etc. and in this regard, in all cases, the competence of the design team and its high responsibility and professionalism are a guarantee for ensuring the reliability and safety of the constructed installation.

Making mistakes in the design can lead to serious accidents or damage to various elements of the installation, as well as to the elements and equipment located around it. But even if the project is made in the best way, it can be compromised if the subsequent

processes of installation and operation are carried out by low-qualified and irresponsible employees. For this, it is extremely important to apply a systematic approach to the entire process, from the design phase of the gas regulation installation, through its construction and subsequent operation. To solve this task, the design team must control the implementation of the project created by them, both at the "installation" and at the "operation" stage. In this way, the risk of poor-quality installation of the gas regulation installation and its incompetent operation will be eliminated.

2. Influence of the various components in determining the reliability of the design of the gas regulation installations

2.1 Criteria determined by the contracting authority

These are criteria that the future owner of the gas regulation installation, in his capacity as the contractor for its design, sets for the design team. These criteria are related to determining the input and output pressure of the natural gas, the required flow rate, the location of the installation, requirements for the deployment of additional measuring and filtering fittings, other than those specified by the regulatory documents, etc..

To ensure a high degree of reliability of the installation, the designer must know all the elements and materials that he plans to use. When he has more than one element or unit that he can use, he must analyze and compare their design features and reliability characteristics in order to choose the most applicable component for his designed facility, ensuring a high degree of reliability, safety and compliance with the requirements set by the contracting authority.

Often in production processes that are continuous, it is necessary to provide the possibility to replace the pressure regulator in case it fails or to replace the gas filter if it is found to be clogged. These criteria (requirements) set by the contracting authority to the designer must be met, although they are not mandatory

from the point of view of regulatory documents. In this case, the designer must know well the different structural schemes in order to be able to choose the

most correct technical solution. Figure 1 shows a structural diagram for the parallel arrangement of two pressure regulators.

Figure 1

Figure 2 shows a diagram for the sequential arrangement of two pressure regulators.

Figure 2

p_1 is the value of the incoming pressure of natural gas, and p_2 is the value of the pressure after its adjustment and its supply to the gas installation or pipeline to the final consumer.

From the two diagrams shown, it can be seen that in case of failure of the main working regulator (Reg.1) in parallel installation, it is possible to switch the gas supply through the backup regulator (Reg.2) quickly enough (just by manipulating the shut-off valves) without the serviced technological process is interrupted and the main regulator is repaired or replaced at the same time. Using the sequential arrangement scheme, it is seen that the second (spare) regulator is in the passive state, i.e. it cannot be put into working condition immediately after the failure of the main regulator (Reg.1). In this case, it will be necessary for the designer to extend the connection scheme, finding a suitable way to ensure easy and quick inclusion of the backup regulator (Reg.2) in operation and the possibility to replace or repair the damaged main regulator without stopping the supply of gas to the final consumer. Interruption of the operation of the main regulator can occur for several main reasons: in case of membrane failure; in case of spring failure; when mechanical impurities enter; when the regulator is destroyed. The reliable operation of the system also depends on the correct choice of the installation scheme. This is achieved by knowing well the type of expected failures and the probability that they will

occur. By preliminary study of the reliability of the elements in the designed installation and performing an accurate reliability analysis, it is possible to reduce the number of potential rejections that would occur and at the same time to evaluate the causes and processes that cause these rejections. In this way, it is possible to achieve quality design to a significant extent while guaranteeing high reliability and safe and long-term operation of the gas regulating installation for natural gas.

3. Determination of possible rejections in the gas regulation installation

In this type of installation, the aspiration of all elements in it is to guarantee a persistent and stable output parameter (p_2). Changing this parameter and going beyond the specified operating limits will indicate that the operability of one or more elements of the system has been impaired. This shows that each of the elements can have an impact on the output parameter, which significantly complicates the performance of a reliable analysis of random events that would provoke system rejections. To achieve better results when performing reliability analysis, possible rejections can be examined and summarised. Rejections can be grouped as follows:

- **Group 1:** Rejections leading to the shutdown of the gas regulation installation, i.e. $p_2 = 0$
- **Group 2:** Rejections in elements with a high degree of reliability where the probability of

occurrence is extremely low. Such elements are steel pipes that are part of the designed installation. Such failures will not have a significant impact on the operability of the gas control system and can be determined that they will not affect the change in the p_2

- **Group 3:** Rejections of elements that can be repaired or replaced during the operation of the installation, without having a significant impact on its operability. By means of an appropriate connection scheme ensuring a higher degree of reliability, elements of group 1 can also be placed in the group of these Rejections. Refusals from this group have no effect on p_2

- **Group 4:** Rejections of elements that cannot be repaired or replaced without stopping the process of operation of the installation. These elements include shut-off valves, threaded and flange connections, etc. Rejections from this group affect the performance of the installation. For the time during which the relevant operations are carried out on the elements of this group, the impact on the value of p_2 will be negative and $p_2=0$, but at the same time the working condition of the main elements and assemblies of the gas regulating installation will be preserved

As a result of the definition of these main groups, it can be concluded that when drawing up the structural

diagram for the reliability of the installation, only the rejections that are defined in Group 1 are essential.

4. Drawing up a structural diagram of the reliability of the gas regulating installation and determining the probability of trouble-free operation

To draw up the structural reliability diagram, it is necessary to build a logical model for the operation of the system in the absence of rejections, assuming that it will operate in the mode of only occurring independent and sudden failures or gradual rejections occurring under certain conditions, as a result of which the installation can be located in only two stable states: working and not working. When determining the structural diagram for the reliability of the system, it is necessary to depict all the connections between the individual elements. It is important to note that the structural diagram (Figures 4a and 4b) does not always coincide with the structural diagram actually drawn up by the designer (Figures 3a and 3b) of connecting the elements of the installation. Figure 3a shows a typical principal design diagram of a natural gas control system, and Figure 3b shows a design diagram with additional requirements for duplication of the filter and regulator requested by the contracting authority.

Figure 3a

Figure 3b

F1 and F1' are the main and backup filters, respectively, and R1 and R1' are the main and backup pressure regulators. p_1 and p_2 are the inlet and outlet

pressures, and p_2 is the result of the operation of the installation, as a complex system.

Figures 4a and 4b show the structural reliability diagrams corresponding to Figures 3a and 3b.

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 4a shows a structural diagram of five consecutively connected elements of the pressure control installation, in which case it is identical to the structural diagram shown in Figure 3a. The probability of uptime N of each of the elements over a period of time t is respectively $N_1(t)$, $N_2(t)$, $N_3(t)$, $N_4(t)$ and $N_5(t)$. The probability of failure-free operation of the plant for the same period of time t will be

$$N(t) = N_1 \cdot N_2 \cdot N_3 \cdot N_4 \cdot N_5$$

The installation shown in structural diagram 3b and structural diagram 4b has a similar development to diagrams 3a and 4a, but the main elements 2 and 4 are duplicated in order to guarantee an uninterrupted work process in case of failure. In this case, the probability of trouble-free operation of the installation will be

$$N(t) = N_1 \left[1 - (1 - N_2)^2 \right] \cdot N_3 \left[1 - (1 - N_4)^2 \right] \cdot N_4 \cdot N_5$$

When using structural diagrams to assess the reliability of pressure regulation installations, it is important to consider the degree of reliability of each of the elements that make them up. As a compromise to create a sufficiently reliable installation, the designer can balance the reliabilities of the individual elements by providing for the elements with a higher risk of failure to be of higher quality and manufacturer-guaranteed reliability, and those with a lower risk to be of the highest quality and thus compensate for the price difference of the former without reducing the overall reliability of the installation. A basic action to ensure the reliability of an installation during its design is to ensure a sufficient margin in the main parameters of the elements, such as strength, wear resistance, impact resistance, vibration resistance, weather resistance, etc..

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